

DIGITAL MARKETING SKILLS NEEDED BY BUSINESS EDUCATION STUDENTS IN PUBLIC TERTIARY INSTITUTIONS IN CROSS RIVER STATE FOR BUSINESS SUCCESS UPON GRADUATION

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Abstract

The study determined the digital marketing skills needed by business education students in public tertiary institutions in Cross River State, Nigeria. Three specific purposes and research questions covering email marketing skills, social media marketing skills and e-commerce skills and three null hypotheses guided the study. Descriptive survey design was adopted for the study. The population comprised 94 Business Educators in four tertiary institutions in Cross River State offering business education programmes. The entire population was studied without sampling since the size was not too large. The instrument for data collection was researchers-designed four rating scale questionnaire titled: Digital Marketing Skills Rating Scale (DMSRS). The instrument was validated by three experts and was tested for reliability using Cronbach Alpha coefficient which produced reliability coefficient value of 0.78. Mean and standard deviation were used to answer the research questions and determine the homogeneity of the respondents' means while t-test was used to test the null hypotheses at 0.05 level of significance. Findings indicated that the three digital marketing skills used in the study are needed by business education students to a very large extent. Also, there was no significant difference between the mean ratings of respondents on the extent business education students need the three social media marketing skills used in the study as a result of institution type, institution ownership and gender. Based on the findings, it was concluded that by adequately developing the three digital marketing skills used in the study, business education graduates can position themselves as valuable assets to any organization seeking to enhance its online presence and reach. It was recommended among others that public tertiary institutions need to adapt their curriculum to meet industry standards by integrating essential skills like email marketing, social media and e-commerce to enable students stay ahead of the curve and thrive in the competitive business landscape.

Keywords: Digital marketing skills, email marketing, social marketing and e-commerce marketing

Introduction

Digital marketing is an arrangement between a seller and buyer to exchange product or service for money

using technologies and online channels. Desai (2019) conceived digital marketing as the marketing of products or services using digital technologies,

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mainly on the Internet, but also including mobile phones, display advertising, and any other digital media. It involves executing advertising campaigns and effective communication with target audience via digital channels and media. The main objective of digital marketing is the exchange of goods towards the service sector, which mainly involves interactivity, connectivity and customer relationship building (Jha et al., 2016). In other words, main objective of digital marketing is to maintain the loyalty of existing online customers and to attract potential customers. Digital marketing comes in different types such as email marketing, social media marketing, Search Engine Optimization (SEO), display advertising, Search Engine Marketing (SEM), events and webinars, A/B testing and website optimization, content marketing, video marketing, marketing analytics, marketing automation, Customer Relationship Management (CRM), Content Management System (CMS), Pay-per-click (PPC) advertising, LinkedIn Ads and affiliate marketing (Jitsinh et al., 2018:89). Globally, digital marketing is growing at a tremendous rate, and this is opening up new avenues for businesses (Išoraitė, 2020). Studies on digital marketing indicates increase scholastic interest in the area. For instance, Išoraitė (2020) analysed the peculiarities of digital marketing: the definition of digital marketing, the advantages and disadvantages of digital marketing, and the process of digital marketing. Desai (2019) study focused on conceptual understanding of digital marketing, how digital marketing helps today's business and some cases in the form of examples. Jitsinh et al. (2018) study sheds more lights on the concept of online marketing, impact of online marketing on consumer purchase and traditional marketing versus online marketing. Furthermore, Jha et al. (2016) conducted a study and found that digital marketing can be used as a multipurpose object in the world of commerce. However, attention of scholars have not been directed to digital skills, particularly those business education students need. It is important to note that businesses

are constantly evolving and adapting to the ever-changing landscape of digital marketing. As such, it is crucial for business education students in public tertiary institutions to acquire essential digital marketing skills to stay ahead of the curve and remain competitive in the job market. The focus of digital marketing skills in this study is on email marketing, social media marketing and e-commerce.

Email, the short form for electronic email, refers to digital message sent using the internet from one person to another or multiple recipients using enabled electronic devices. In the opinion of Cloud Flare (2024), email is both the delivery system and individual messages that are sent and received. El-Sabban (2015) stated that email is an efficient system for disseminating information to the academic community and for receiving almost instant feedback. Email marketing is an online communication strategy aimed to achieve lead generation, contacts nurturing and sales promotion. Rettie in Sabbagh (2021) was of the opinion that email marketing is increasingly recognized as an effective internet-marketing tool. Thus, many companies use email marketing as a way of communicating and keeping contact with their audience (Desai, 2019). Effective use of email requires certain skills. Test Gorilla (2024) considered email marketing skills as the abilities email marketers required to handle their responsibilities. At least, email marketers should be able to automate, analyse, edit and make sure email messages are getting to the right inboxes and at the right time (Donk, 2021).

Social media marketing skill, which also covered in the study is the ability to use social media platforms to promote a product or service in order to reach a wider audience. Nadaraja and Yazdanifard (2013) defined social media marketing as the use of social media channels to promote a company and its products. Social media marketing skills are indispensable for businesses looking to succeed in the digital age. These skills help businesses to connect with their target audience effectively. Developing a combination of technical, creative, and analytical

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skills among others could be key to effective social media marketing.

E-commerce, the short form for electronic commerce, is the buying and selling of products or services over the internet. It is a digital marketplace which has revolutionized the way people buy and sell goods and services online. With the advancements in technology and increase in internet usage, online shopping has become increasingly popular, providing a seamless experience for users. The convenience of browsing various products and making purchases at any time has attracted a wide audience to e-commerce platforms. eTrade for all (2021) observed that e-commerce can only be effective if the people managing and engaging with it have the right skills. E-commerce skills are essential in digital economy. Whether an individual looking to start a career in e-commerce or a business owner looking to expand online presence, having the right skills is crucial. Developing a diverse set of e-commerce skills could be essential for success in the digital marketplace especially for business education students.

Statement of the Problem

Traditional marketing has not been very efficient in tracking customers' information necessary to transform relationship between buyers and sellers and in making informed decisions timely. Traditional marketing is limited because it uses offline strategies which focus around product, price, promotion and place (4Ps). Another problem with traditional marketing is that less emphasis is given to customers whose loyalty is imperative for business success. Thus, a shift to digital marketing which focus around customers is necessary, especially in the current digital era. Digital marketing strategies are engaging and encompasses content, community, connection and conversation (4Cs). However, the shift to digital marketing appears to be challenged by lack of digital marketing skills among business practioners. Paradoxically, in digital economy, digital marketing skills are increasingly demanded in the job market as more businesses are relying on digital marketing

strategies to reach their target audience. Therefore, having a solid understanding of digital marketing skills is crucial for business education students. Unfortunately, the general lack of digital marketing curriculum in colleges and universities particularly in Cross River State, combined with limited opportunities for practical hands-on training, has led to graduates that are unprepared to take advantage of digital marketing, as their specific knowledge and skills related to digital marketing remain limited. This makes it imperative to conduct this study to determine the digital marketing skills needed by business education students in public tertiary institutions in order to provide empirical data for necessary actions by relevant stakeholders.

Purpose of the Study

The main purpose of the study was to determine the digital marketing skills needed by business education students in public tertiary institutions in Cross River State for business success upon graduation. Specifically, the study ascertained the:

1. Email marketing skills needed by business education students in public tertiary institutions in Cross River State for business success upon graduation.
2. Social media marketing skills needed by business education students in public tertiary institutions in Cross River State for business success upon graduation.
3. E-commerce skills needed by business education students in public tertiary institutions in Cross River State for business success upon graduation.

Research Questions

The following research questions were formulated for the study:

1. To what extent are email marketing skills needed by business education students in public tertiary institutions in Cross River State for business success upon graduation?
2. To what extent are social media marketing skills needed by business education students in

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public tertiary institutions in Cross River State for business success upon graduation?

3. To what extent are e-commerce skills needed by business education students in public tertiary institutions in Cross River State for business success upon graduation?

Hypotheses

The following null hypotheses guided the study and were tested at 0.05 level of significance:

1. There is no significant difference between the mean ratings of respondents in colleges of education and universities on the extent business education students in public tertiary institutions in Cross River State need email marketing skills for business success upon graduation.
2. There is no significant difference between the mean ratings of respondents in federal and state owned institutions in Cross River State on the extent to which social media marketing skills are needed by business education students in public tertiary institutions for business success upon graduation.
3. There is no significant difference between the mean ratings of male and female respondents on the extent to which e-commerce skills are needed by business education students in public tertiary

institutions in Cross River State need for business success upon graduation.

Methodology

Descriptive survey design was adopted for the study. The population comprised 94 Business Educators in four tertiary institutions in Cross River State offering business education programme. The entire population was studied without sampling because the size was not too large. The instrument for data collection was a researcher’s self-designed four-point rating scale questionnaire entitled “Digital Marketing Skills Rating Scale (DMSRS)”. The instrument was validated by experts and was tested for reliability using Cronbach Alpha coefficient which produce a coefficient of 0.78. Mean and standard deviation were used to answer the research questions and determine the homogeneity of the respondents’ mean ratings. Grand mean score was used to answer the research questions based on a 4-point rating scale of very much needed (3.50-4.00), much needed (2.50-3.49), little needed (1.50-2.49), very little needed (0.50-1.49). T-test was used to test the null hypotheses at alpha level of 0.05. A null hypothesis was not rejected where the calculated-t value was less than the critical-t value, otherwise it was rejected.

Results

Table 1: Respondents’ Mean and Standard Deviation Ratings on the Extent Business Education Students in Cross River State Need Email Marketing Skills for Business Success upon Graduation

S/N	Email marketing skills include ability to:	\bar{X}	SD	REMARKS
1	Create a subject line that is attention-grabbing	3.61	0.53	Very Much Needed
2	Send follow-up emails to website visitors who downloaded something	3.58	0.51	Very Much Needed
3	Send new customers welcome messages that captivate them	3.63	0.50	Very Much Needed
4	Send holiday promotions messages to loyalty programmed members	3.55	0.54	Very Much Needed
5	Personalize emails to cater to the specific needs of each segment	3.68	0.46	Very Much Needed
6	Manage email list effectively	3.64	0.47	Very Much Needed
7	Securing emails from cyber-attacks	3.55	0.54	Very Much Needed
Grand Mean		3.60		Very Much Needed

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Table 1 reveals that the items mean scores ranges between 3.55 and 3.68 indicating that all the email marketing skills are very much needed. The grand mean of 3.60 reveals that, in the opinion of the respondents, email marketing skills are very much needed by business education students in public

tertiary institutions in Cross River State for business success upon graduation. The standard deviation for all the items are within the same range which indicates that the respondents were homogeneous in their mean ratings.

Table 2: Respondents' Mean and Standard Deviation Ratings on the Extent Business Education Students in Cross River State Need Social Media Marketing Skills for Business Success upon Graduation

S/N	Social media marketing skills include ability to:	\bar{X}	SD	RMKS
8	Define target audience	3.70	0.48	Very Much Needed
9	Creating engaging content	3.51	0.52	Very Much Needed
10	Interpret insights from frequent customers' comments	3.65	0.51	Very Much Needed
11	Build relationships with followers	3.65	0.51	Very Much Needed
12	Managing online communities	3.58	0.51	Very Much Needed
13	Making data-driven decisions	3.57	0.53	Very Much Needed
14	Create interactions by customizing information for individual customers	3.64	0.50	Very Much Needed
Grand Mean		3.61		Very Much Needed

Table 2 shows the items mean scores ranges between 3.70 and 3.51 indicating that all the social media marketing skills are very much needed. The grand mean of 3.61 reveals that, in the opinion of the respondents, social media marketing skills are very much needed by business education students in public

tertiary institutions in Cross River State for business success upon graduation. The standard deviation for all the items are within the same range which indicates that the respondents were homogeneous in their mean rating.

Table 3: Respondents' Mean and Standard Deviation Ratings on the Extent Business Education Students in Cross River State Need E-commerce Skills for Business Success upon Graduation

S/N	E-commerce skills include the ability to:	\bar{X}	SD	RMKS
15	Negotiate deals with suppliers	3.57	0.51	Very Much Needed
16	Secure an electronic wallet	3.57	0.49	Very Much Needed
17	Provide excellent customer support to build trust	3.61	0.48	Very Much Needed
18	Conduct supply chain management	3.68	0.49	Very Much Needed
19	Utilize tools like Google Analytics to track and analyse e-commerce websites performance	3.58	0.53	Very Much Needed
20	Carryout marketing automation	3.58	0.51	Very Much Needed
21	Utilize search engine optimization to drive traffic to e-commerce sites	3.47	0.50	Very Much Needed
Grand Mean		3.58		Very Much Needed

Table 3 shows that the items mean scores ranges between 3.68 and 3.57 indicating that all the e-commerce skills are very much needed. The grand mean of 3.58 reveals that, in the opinion of the respondents, e-commerce skills are very much needed by business education students in public tertiary institutions in Cross River State

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for business success upon graduation. The standard deviation for all the items are within the same range which indicates that the respondents were homogeneous in their mean ratings.

Table 4: Summary of t-test Analysis of The Mean Ratings of Respondents in Colleges of Education and Universities on the Extent to Business Education Students in Public Tertiary Institutions in Cross River State Need Email Marketing Skills for Business Success upon Graduation

Item	Institution	N= 94	Mean	Std.	t-cal	t-crit	Df	Remarks
1	Colleges	46	3.65	0.52	0.62	1.98	92	NS
	Universities	48	3.58	0.53				
2	Colleges	46	3.60	0.53	0.43	1.98	92	NS
	Universities	48	3.56	0.50				
3	Colleges	46	3.60	0.49	0.55	1.98	92	NS
	Universities	48	3.66	0.51				
4	Colleges	46	3.54	0.54	0.16	1.98	92	NS
	Universities	48	3.56	0.54				
5	Colleges	46	3.67	0.47	0.14	1.98	92	NS
	Universities	48	3.68	0.46				
6	Colleges	46	3.63	0.48	0.36	1.98	92	NS
	Universities	48	3.66	0.47				
7	Colleges	46	3.47	0.58	1.31	1.98	92	NS
	Universities	48	3.62	0.48				
					0.51			NS

*NS = Not Significant

Table 4 shows that the calculate-t value for each of the items is less than the table value. This indicates that there was no significant difference in the mean ratings of respondents on all the items based on institution type. The grand calculated t-value of 0.51 shows that there is no significant difference between

the mean ratings of respondents in colleges of education and universities on the extent business education students in Cross River State need email marketing skills for business success upon graduation. The null hypothesis was, therefore, not rejected.

Table 5: Summary of t-test analysis of the mean responses of respondents in in federal and state owned institutions on the extent to which social media marketing skills are needed by business education students in public tertiary institutions

Item	Ownership	N= 94	Mean	Std.	t-cal	t-crit	Df	Rmks
8	Federal	64	3.67	0.50	0.88	1.98	92	NS
	State	30	3.76	0.43				
9	Federal	64	3.50	0.50	0.28	1.98	92	NS
	State	30	3.53	0.57				
10	Federal	64	3.70	0.52	1.19	1.98	92	NS
	State	30	3.56	0.40				
11	Federal	64	3.57	0.55	2.26	1.98	92	Reject
	State	30	3.83	0.37				
12	Federal	64	3.60	0.49	0.66	1.98	92	NS
	State	30	3.53	0.57				
13	Federal	64	3.60	0.55	0.91	1.98	92	NS
	State	30	3.50	0.50				
14	Federal	64	3.62	0.51	0.67	1.98	92	NS
	State	30	3.70	0.46				
					0.97			NS

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*NS = Not Significant

Table 5 shows that the calculated-t value for item 11 is greater than the critical-t value of 1.98 and it is rejected. The calculate-t value for the rest of the items is less than the critical-t value. The grand calculated value of 0.97 suggest that there is no significant difference in the mean rating of respondents in federal

and state owned institutions on the extent to which social media marketing skills are needed by business education students in public tertiary institutions Cross River State for business success upon graduation. The null hypothesis was, therefore, not rejected.

Table 6: Summary of t-test analysis of male and female on the extent to which e-commerce skills needed by business education students in public tertiary institutions in Cross River State for Business Success upon Graduation

Item	Gender	N= 73	Mean	Std.	t-cal	t-crit	Df	Rmks
15	Male	56	3.62	0.48	1.15	1.98	92	NS
	Female	38	3.50	0.55				
16	Male	56	3.60	0.49	0.77	1.98	92	NS
	Female	38	3.52	0.50				
17	Male	56	3.67	0.47	1.49	1.98	92	NS
	Female	38	3.52	0.50				
18	Male	56	3.69	0.46	0.37	1.98	92	NS
	Female	38	3.65	0.53				
19	Male	56	3.58	0.53	0.09	1.98	92	NS
	Female	38	3.57	0.55				
20	Male	56	3.62	0.48	0.90	1.98	92	NS
	Female	38	3.52	0.55				
21	Male	56	3.50	0.50	0.49	1.98	92	NS
	Female	38	3.44	0.50				
					0.75			NS

*NS = Not Significant

Table 4 shows that all the items are accepted because each of the calculate-t value is less than the critical-t value. The calculated grand mean value of 0.75 suggest that there is no significant difference in the mean rating of male and female respondents on the extent to which e-commerce skills needed by business education students in public tertiary institutions.

Discussion

Findings of the study shows that, in the opinion of the respondents, email marketing skills are very much needed by business education students in public tertiary institutions in Cross River State for business success upon graduation. Email is a fundamental form of communication in the digital age and has also become an important marketing tool to reach out to individuals and organizations. Having the skills to utilize emails in marketing is, therefore, very essential for business education students who may venture into

entrepreneurship upon graduation since they critical for any marketer looking to reach their audience effectively and efficiently. With the rise of digital communication, mastering email marketing can make all the difference in engaging with customers and driving sales. The finding agrees with Test Gorilla (2024) that email marketing skills are required by email marketers to handle their responsibilities as they facilitate connection, information sharing and collaboration among people across the globe regardless of location and time. The finding also aligns with that of Sabbagh (2021) that skills in email marketing campaigns help to increase the sale of products in electronic shops and to target customers efficiently and legally thereby helping marketers to focus on target market, find new customers, retain them and stay in connected with them at low cost. The Findings further revealed that significant

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difference did not exist in respondents' mean ratings as a result of institution type. This means that all business education students, regardless of type of institution, need email marketing skills at a very great extent for business success upon graduation.

Findings indicated that social media marketing skills are very much needed by business education students in public tertiary institutions in Cross River State for business success upon graduation. These skills are among the digital skills highly needed in digital era and are capable of making business education students globally competitive. The finding aligns with Ravi and Sujaya (2021) that skills in social media marketing empowers people through online social networks to advertise their websites, goods, or services and to engage with and tap into a much wider audience that would not have been possible through conventional advertising channels. Social media marketing has become an integral part of the marketing strategy for businesses in the digital age. It offers unique platforms for businesses to connect with their target audience, build brand awareness, and drive sales. It allows businesses to reach a large audience and engage with them in real-time. It also helps in building brand loyalty and increasing customer retention. Findings further revealed that there is no significant difference in the mean rating of respondents in federal and state owned institutions on the extent to which social media marketing skills are needed by business education students in public tertiary institutions. The findings indicates that institution ownership is not sensitive to social media marketing skills needed by students. Online socialization has improved significantly, with more users utilizing social media platforms to stay connected. Skills in social media marketing is essential. The finding agrees with Ozioma (2023) that skills in social media marketing has significant impact on consumer patronage intention, consumer patronage and repeat purchase. Finding of the study revealed that e-commerce skills are very much needed by business education students in public tertiary

institutions in Cross River State for business success upon graduation. With more people using internet in recent times, many people turning to online shopping. E-commerce has seen exponential growth in recent years and it has the potential to transform the retail landscape, offering convenience and variety to consumers. Having e-commerce skill in digital marketplace is necessary for effective buying and selling of goods and services online. The finding agrees with eTrade for all (2021) that e-commerce can only be effective if the people managing and engaging with it have the right skills. The change in technology which witnessed a shift e-commerce requires that business education students should not be left out in acquiring necessary digital skills. The finding agrees with Klaiber et al. (2015) that e-commerce skills are required in the international retail sector by users to cope with the changing. The finding agree also with Binuomote et al. (2022) that business education students required ecommerce skills for entrepreneurial development in the 21st century. Findings further revealed that there is no significant difference in the mean rating of male and female respondents on the extent to which e-commerce skills needed by business education students in public tertiary institutions. The finding implies that e-commerce skills is not subjected to a particular gender. E-commerce skills are skills needed by everyone who wishes to be successful in digital marketing. The finding is in line with Edokpolor and Chukwu (2017) that there was no significant difference in the mean rating of male and female OTM education students on the extent to which they have acquired competencies required in e-commerce. The finding also agrees with Binuomote et al. (2022) that there is no significant difference in the mean rating of the male and female Business education lecturers on e-commerce marketing skills required by Business education students in Nigeria.

Conclusion

The study revealed that digital marketing skills are greatly needed by business education students in

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public tertiary institutions in Cross River State for success in the highly competitive digital business landscape upon graduation, regardless of institution type, ownership and gender. By adequately developing email marketing skills, social media marketing skills and e-commerce marketing skills, business education graduates can position themselves as valuable assets to any organization seeking to enhance its online presence and reach. Based on these findings, it was concluded that investing in digital marketing skills generally and specifically in email marketing, social media e-commerce, is not only beneficial for the students' career growth but also essential for their continued success and growth in business in the digital era.

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Based on the findings and conclusion of the study, the following recommendations were made: Public tertiary institutions should adapt their curriculum to meet industry standards by integrating essential skills like digital marketing skills to enable students stay ahead of the curve and thrive in the competitive business landscape. Public tertiary institutions should collaborate with digital marketing experts to mentor business education students and help them develop essential digital marketing skills that will enhance their competitiveness in the digital era.

Business education students should leverage on digital marketing skills like email marketing, social media marketing and e-commerce marketing skills to be competitive in digitally driven economy.

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